

Towards the assessment of perceptual style

Hendrik N.J. Schifferstein, Department of Industrial Design, Delft University of Technology - The Netherlands,

Monique A.M. Smeets, Department of Clinical and Health Psychology - the Netherlands

Abstract

People may differ in the extent to which they use and rely on their different sensory modalities, i.e. their perceptual styles. A user's perceptual style may affect how he or she interacts with a product, and what he or she appreciates in the product. Therefore, designers need to be aware of their own perceptual style and of the perceptual styles of the people who use their products.

In a first attempt to develop an empirical measure of perceptual style, we transformed Peck and Childers' (2003) Need For Touch scale into equivalent scales for all sensory modalities: the Need for Sensory Stimulation Scales. Each scale consists of two sub-scales, one measuring the extent to which a person enjoys receiving sensory information and spontaneously searches for that stimulation (autotelic) and the other one measuring the extent to which a person uses sensory input for making a decision about a product (instrumental). In a sample with an age and gender distribution comparable to the general population (N=96), the senses tended to cluster into two groups: vision and touch versus taste, smell, and audition. A cluster analysis suggested a distinction between four groups of individuals: people with high versus low needs for sensory information for all modalities, and people with primarily instrumental versus autotelic needs for sensory information. Mean responses of 38 design students were significantly higher than the general sample for touch, vision, and audition. They were equal for smell, and lower for instrumental taste.

Furthermore, we started to develop a new instrument from scratch to measure perceptual style for a single modality: The Odor Awareness Scale. The scale consists of items that describe situations and common products that people tend to encounter in everyday situations and asks about their reactions towards these odors. A principal components analysis of the responses of 332 students revealed one factor that measured general odor awareness, one that indicated whether people noticed alarming smells, one factor was associated with body odors, and one factor assessed the role of odors in product purchase.

The first approach has provided a simple questionnaire instrument that gives a quick estimate of a person's perceptual style, which can be used for illustrative purposes during design education. The second approach has yielded a new instrument that can help to predict how people respond to scented products. If a similar approach is used to develop scales for the other modalities as well, they can form a set of instruments that give a detailed insight into a person's perceptual style.

Keywords: senses

Introduction

People may differ in the extent to which they use and rely on their different sensory modalities. Some people may rely more on visual information, whereas others rely mainly on auditory inputs, or depend primarily on tactual or chemosensory input. Such differences might originate from differences in perceptual sensitivities, but also from differences in the cognitive abilities to process information received through a specific sensory channel. Perceptual style refers to the way in which and the extent to which a person makes use of the information that is gathered by the various senses.

Some people's style may be better adjusted to some situations than to others. This may affect their ability to cope with the situation. If people differ in the way in which they rely on their different sensory channels, it may have consequences for the ways in which people acquire information and learn new capabilities. It may have an effect on how people store information and, consequently, the content of their memories. In education, it may be necessary to teach children certain principles in multiple sensory ways, because some may find it easier to comprehend information provided through touch than through audition or vision. Also, it may affect people's need for information and, thereby, influence their buying behavior. During the marketing of products, it may be necessary to distribute different types of information in order to appeal to different groups of people. Differences in perceptual style may partly explain why some consumers tend to buy products from catalogues and through the Internet where mainly visual information is presented, whereas others only buy in retail stores where they can physically examine the products by touch.

It is important for designers to realize that a person's perceptual style may affect how users interact with a product and what they appreciate in the product. A person who uses the senses in a different way, may also use and evaluate a product differently. In addition, it is important for a designer to be aware of his or her own personal perceptual style. A designer who focuses on a single modality is likely to develop products that excel in desirable stimuli for that particular modality but that neglect the other modalities. For example, improving only the visual appearance of a product may easily lead to a product that smells bad, makes unwanted sounds, or is unpleasant to touch. Such a product will only appeal to others who are vision-oriented. On the other hand, a designer who distributes attention over all the modalities is likely to produce products that appeal to people with multiple perceptual styles. Therefore,

when a designer is aware that he or she has the tendency to neglect a particular modality, this modality probably requires some extra effort during the design process.

Although the idea that people may differ in the way they use their senses frequently occurs in the popular press, it has been touched upon only incidentally in the scientific literature. For example, Marsella and Higginbotham (1973) proposed that the senses actively mediate the organismic-environmental interaction, which can be seen as the basis of human behaviour. They defined a sensory type as a 'relatively consistent and enduring pattern of sensory responsiveness to stimulation which facilitates the organism's adaptation and adjustment to its environment' (p. 11). In their approach, a sensory type 'manifests itself in terms of recognition thresholds, discrimination thresholds, and habituation thresholds' (p. 12).

To test this line of reasoning, Shizuru and Marsella (1981) determined the performance of Japanese-American and Caucasian-American male students in performance tests employing the visual, auditory, and tactual-kinaesthetic modalities. Even though the groups displayed approximately equal perceptual sensitivity, these authors found distinctions in the organization of sensory information. The students with a Japanese background relied most heavily upon spatial-kinaesthetic information, whereas the Caucasian students were more visually oriented. In addition, the Caucasian students tended to take an integrated, multi-modal approach to complex stimulus situations, whereas the Japanese relied predominantly on a single modality at a time. These data suggest that differences in perceptual styles may originate from cultural differences.

Another example of cultural differences is described by Wober (1966). In an American population, the results of the Rod and Frame Test (RFT) that assesses the analytic ability to separate proprioceptive input from visual input usually tend to be closely related to those of equivalent visual tests. However, Wober (1966) found that the test results were not related to those of the Embedded Figures Test among Nigerians. This discrepancy probably occurs because visual analytic ability is trained through Western education, but not in Nigerian society.

Scholars in the area of Neuro-Linguistic Programming (NLP) (O'Connor and Seymour, 1993) have suggested that people process reality through several sensory or representational systems. They suggest that thoughts and feelings are structured according to these systems.

According to these scholars the visual, auditory, and kinaesthetic systems are used most in Western cultures. Taste and smell are judged to be less important and are often included in the kinaesthetic system. Individuals do not use these systems to the same degree, and seem to have a preference for one or, possibly, two of these systems. The system that an individual uses most of the time is called the Preferred Representational System (PRS). Unfortunately, the empirical evidence used to support the existence of a PRS is inconclusive. Typically, three different tests are described in the NLP literature to determine the PRS: eye movements in response to specific questions, word choice in conversations, and self-reports on people's preferred sensory system, but the results of these three tests hardly correlate over individuals (Sharpley, 1984; Sharpley, 1987).

Study 1: The Need for Sensory Stimulation Scales

Besides the finding that the measures of the PRS are not consistent, we think that it is more plausible to assume that each person finds all sensory systems important to a certain degree, and that the relative degrees of importance for all the senses are the best indicators for how that person interacts with the environment. This would argue for the development of a perceptual profile that assesses the degrees to which all modalities are relevant for a person.

As a first attempt to develop such a measure, we modified an existing measure developed for the tactual modality to apply to all sensory modalities. Peck and Childers' (2003) Need For Touch scale is a 12-item questionnaire instrument that assesses a person's preference for the extraction and utilization of information obtained through the haptic system in the context of product purchase. This scale consists of two sub-scales of six items each. One sub-scale measures the extent to which a person enjoys receiving tactile information and spontaneously searches for tactile stimulation (autotelic) and the other measures the extent to which a person uses tactile input for making a decision about a product (instrumental). We modified the items so that they referred to product usage in general, instead of the buying process. We translated and transformed the original items into twelve equivalent items for vision, audition, smell, and taste. Examples of items are 'If I cannot see the appearance of a product in a store, I do not buy it' (vision, instrumental), 'I have more confidence in my evaluation of a product after holding it' (touch, instrumental), 'I like to listen to the sound of things even if I have no intention of using these things' (audition, autotelic), and 'When browsing, I like to smell all kinds of things on my way' (smell, autotelic). In this way we developed Need for Touch,

Vision, Audition, Olfaction, and Gustation scales, that all consisted of two subscales. All items were presented in random order and were rated on a 7 point scale ranging from ‘disagree completely’ to ‘agree completely’.

The questionnaire was first administered to 96 respondents of a quota sample that roughly mirrored the general adult population with respect to age and gender. The men (N=48) ranged in age from 13 to 59 years (mean 35.6, SD 15.5) and the women (N=48) ranged from 12 to 56 years (mean 34.3 SD 14.2).

The psychometric properties of the several scales were satisfactory (Table 1). Cronbach’s α values varied from 0.77 to 0.91 for the five autotelic scales and from 0.70 to 0.84 for the five instrumental scales. Within each modality, the correlation between the two subscales varied from 0.34 (Taste) to 0.67 (Smell). This indicates that the two dimensions measure related, but different constructs.

Table 1. Internal consistency (Cronbach’s α) of subscales (6 items), the total scale (12 items), and the Pearson correlation between subscales of the Need for Sensory Stimulation Scales for the five separate modalities

	Autotelic	Instrumental	Total	Correlation subscales
# items	6	6	12	
Vision	0.80	0.70	0.83	0.53
Touch	0.91	0.76	0.88	0.52
Smell	0.85	0.83	0.90	0.67
Hearing	0.80	0.84	0.86	0.51
Taste	0.77	0.74	0.79	0.34

Subsequently, we looked at the correlations between the modalities (Table 2). For the autotelic scales, we find the highest correlation between vision and touch (0.68), smell and hearing (0.60), and smell and taste (0.55). For the instrumental scales, we find the highest correlations between taste and smell (0.74), smell and hearing (0.63), and vision and touch

(0.60). Given that the three highest coefficients are found again for the same pairs of modalities, these analyses tentatively suggest that people roughly distinguish between two kinds of sensory needs: a need for visual and tactual input, versus a need for auditory, olfactory and gustatory input. This grouping of modalities seems to be more pronounced when the sensory information is used to evaluate products (instrumental) than when the sensory input is just used for enjoyment (autotelic). Correlations between the different scales are far from perfect. This suggests that people may have individually different profiles and, consequently, may differ in emphasis on the various modalities.

Table 2. Pearson correlations coefficients between the five modalities for the Autotelic and Instrumental scales

	Vision	Touch	Smell	Hearing
Autotelic				
Touch	0.68			
Smell	0.50	0.53		
Hearing	0.34	0.44	0.60	
Taste	0.42	0.48	0.55	0.40
Instrumental				
Touch	0.60			
Smell	0.23	0.45		
Hearing	0.31	0.36	0.63	
Taste	0.22	0.34	0.74	0.59

To identify groups based on different needs for various types of sensory information, we performed a k-means cluster analysis. The cluster analysis with 4 groups gives the solution shown in Table 3. This solution suggests that the people in our sample cannot be distinguished as see, hear or touch people. Instead, all groups give the highest ratings to vision. Cluster 1 consists of people who rate high on virtually all scales, whereas in Cluster 4 ratings for all modalities are relatively low. Clusters 1 and 4 suggest that we can meaningfully

distinguish two groups with a relatively high need for all types of sensory information versus a relatively low need for any type of sensory information. Clusters 2 and 3, on the other hand, suggest that people may be distinguished on their emphasis on gathering sensory information for fun or using sensory information with a purpose: in Cluster 2, the ratings for the instrumental scales tend to be highest, whereas in Cluster 3 ratings on the autotelic scales tend to be highest.

Table 3. Final cluster centers of the k-means cluster solution.

	Cluster			
	1	2	3	4
<i>N</i>	31	23	24	18
Autotelic				
Vision	5.59	5.10	5.82	4.11
Touch	4.53	3.07	5.01	2.44
Smell	4.82	2.83	4.08	2.56
Hearing	4.95	3.49	4.23	3.16
Taste	4.46	2.93	4.09	3.06
Instrumental				
Vision	5.48	5.54	5.42	4.34
Touch	5.03	4.81	4.55	2.98
Smell	4.98	3.15	3.22	2.52
Hearing	4.63	3.86	3.31	2.64
Taste	5.07	3.90	3.67	3.41

Repeated measures ANOVA of the responses on the ten subscales showed a significant main effect of Modality [$F(3,318)=76.9, p<0.001$] and a significant Modality \times Subscale [$F(4,367)=17.8, p<0.001$] interaction, but no main effect of Subscale [$F(1,95)=1.7, p>0.15$]. As regards the main effect of Modality, responses for vision were larger than responses for any of

the other modalities [t-tailed t-test with Bonferroni adjustment, $p < 0.001$]. In addition, the average ratings for smell were smaller than for touch and taste. As regards the Modality \times Subscale interaction, we found that average ratings for Instrumental and Autotelic were comparable for vision (5.3 and 5.3, respectively) and for smell (3.6 and 3.7). Instrumental ratings tended to be higher for touch (4.5 and 3.9) and taste (4.1 and 3.7), whereas Autotelic ratings tended to be higher for audition (3.7 and 4.1). When Gender was included as a between-subjects variable in this analysis, no additional significant effects were found.

In summary, many differences in means on the scales depend on the modality and the type of subscale (autotelic versus instrumental). However, it may be interesting to use the scales at the individual levels and to develop norms to be able to construct an individual's sensory need profile based on his or her relative position on the sensory scales compared to the overall group.

To determine whether designers may differ in their perceptual profile from the general public, we asked 38 industrial design students who took an elective course in Multi Sensory Design to fill out the same questionnaire. We found that their responses deviated considerably from the responses of the larger sample. The students scored significantly higher for both touch subscales, and for autotelic vision and audition. However, they scored lower for instrumental taste (Table 4). These outcomes suggest that design students interested in this course experience more need for visual, tactual, and auditory information during the interaction with products. However, they do not experience such an increased need for smell or taste information.

Table 4. General sample versus design students (*p<0.05; ** p<0.01)

	General (N=96)	Design students (N=38)
	Mean	Mean
Autotelic		
Vision	5.25	5.85**
Touch	3.91	5.34**
Smell	3.74	3.95
Hearing	4.09	4.52*
Taste	3.74	3.56
Instrumental		
Vision	5.27	5.58
Touch	4.47	5.45**
Smell	3.64	3.52
Hearing	3.74	4.06
Taste	4.13	3.56**

Study 2: Development of the Odor Awareness Scale

Although the scores on the Need for Sensory Stimulation Scales provide us with an interesting perspective on the extent to which and the way in which people need certain types of sensory information, this questionnaire has a number of limitations. First of all, the items address a need for information, which is probably only part of a person's perceptual style. In addition, an often reported drawback of the items used is that they refer to products in general, whereas the importance of sounds may differ, depending on whether one refers to a television set, a vacuum cleaner, or a towel (Schifferstein, 2006), and depending on the context in which the product is used.

Therefore, we decided to develop a new measurement instrument from scratch. We did this only for the sense of smell (Smeets and Schifferstein, 2006). The Odor Awareness Scale aims

to differentiate between people who are aware versus not aware of odors in their environment. The scale consists of items that describe situations and common products that people tend to encounter in everyday situations and asks about their reactions towards these odors. The scale was administered to 332 students from the social sciences, journalism and a technical university. The majority were women (70%); the mean age of the entire sample was 23.9 years (SD = 6.5).

A Principal Components Analyses was conducted on 34 items to explore which meaningful factors would emerge. Several items ($n = 12$) showed considerable overlap in the sense that they loaded high on more than one component. After removal of these items, a 4-component solution emerged that explained 39% of total variance in the dataset (all eigenvalues > 1.0). The first component (explaining 13% of variance) was interpreted as a *general odor awareness* component. People who score high on this component, attach importance to the sense of smell, have an increased tendency to pay attention to odors in their environment or notice sudden smells. Examples of items that load on this factor are: ‘When walking in the woods, do you pay attention to the odors surrounding you?’ and ‘How bothered are you when you cannot smell anything because of a cold or the flue?’. Component 2 (10%) was characterized as *body odors*. People who score high on this component attach importance to how people smell, and are easily attracted or put off by body odors. An example of an item that loaded on this component is: ‘If someone has an unpleasant smell, would you find him or her unattractive?’. Items that were endorsed on the third component (8%) were related to the warning or signal value that off flavors from stale foods can have (e.g., ‘Are you the first to notice the milk has gone sour?’). Anxiety induced by unpleasant smells also loaded on this component, which we have named an *alarm* component. Finally, there was a *product purchase* component (8%). People who value the scent of shower gel, all-purpose cleaner and deodorant over price, packaging, and product effectiveness scored high on this component.

As expected, individuals who score high on the first component also rate their ability to smell as above average ($r = 0.46$, $p < 0.01$). We are currently testing individuals who scored high versus low on the Odor Awareness Scale on a battery of tests to investigate if high scorers indeed have better olfactory abilities than low scorers, and if there are between-group differences in speed of information processing of odor-related information. If high scores on the newly developed scale are indeed correlated with above average abilities, the scale would help predict how individuals respond to smells in their environment or to scented products.

Conclusion

The first approach has provided a simple questionnaire instrument that gives a quick estimate of a person's perceptual style, although the validity of the instrument needs further investigation. It can be used for illustrative purposes during design education. The second approach has yielded a new instrument that is currently being tested. This instrument can help to predict how people respond to scented products. If a similar approach is used to develop scales for the other modalities as well, they can form a set of instruments that give a detailed insight into a person's perceptual style.

Acknowledgements

This research was supported by MAGW VIDI grants 452-02-028 and 452-03-334 of the Netherlands Organization for Scientific Research (N.W.O.) awarded to H.N.J.S and M.A.M.S., respectively. The authors would like to thank Sarah Stuijzand, Nicky Canton, and Sarai Boelema for their contribution to data collection.

References

- Marsella, A. J. and Higginbotham, H. N. (1973) *Sensory types: toward an interactionist model of human behavior*. Honolulu, Hawaii: Department of Psychology, University of Hawaii.
- O'Connor, J. and Seymour, J. (1993) *Introducing NLP - Neurolinguistic Programming - Psychological skills for understanding and influencing people*. London: Harper Collins.
- Peck, J. and Childers, T. L. (2003) "Individual differences in haptic information processing: the "need for touch" scale." *Journal of Consumer Research* 30: 430-442.
- Schifferstein, H. N. J. (2006) "The relative importance of sensory modalities in product usage: a study of self-reports." *Acta Psychologica* 121: 41-64.
- Sharpley, C. F. (1984) "Predicate matching in NLP: a review of research on the preferred representational system." *Journal of Counseling Psychology* 31: 238-248.
- Sharpley, C. F. (1987) "Research findings on neurolinguistic programming: nonsupportive data or untestable theory?" *Journal of Counseling Psychology* 34: 103-107.
- Shizuru, L. S. and Marsella, A. J. (1981) "The sensory processes of Japanese-American and Caucasian-American students." *Journal of Social Psychology* 114: 147-158.
- Smeets, M. A. M. and Schifferstein, H. N. J. (2006) "The relationship between explicit odor awareness, olfactory perceptual ability, and odor information processing." Manuscript in preparation.
- Wober, M. (1966) "Sensotypes." *Journal of Social Psychology* 70: 181-189.